

Diagnostic Utility of Advanced MRI Techniques in the Differentiation of Infective Versus Neoplastic Intracranial Ring Enhancing LesionsSumedha Sirohi¹, Shamimun Nisa², Darsana Behera³, Basanta Manjari Swain⁴, Sangram Panda⁵, Sudhansu Sekhar Mohanty⁶, Mahabir Yadav⁷¹Post Graduate Resident (3rd Year), Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India²Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁴Professor & Head, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁶Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁷Post Graduate Resident (3rd Year), Department of Radiodiagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

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Abstract:**Objectives:** To determine the combined diagnostic performance of advanced MRI Parameters- MRI Diffusion, MRI Perfusion, MR Spectroscopy- in conjunction with conventional MRI sequences for better evaluation of intracranial ring enhancing lesions and differentiation of their infective versus neoplastic etiologies. And deduce the sensitivity and specificity of the combined usage of conventional and advanced MRI techniques in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial ring- enhancing lesions.**Methods:** A total of 60 patients referred to the radiology department were included in the study. Conventional MR sequences, Advanced MR sequences, Magnetic resonance spectroscopy and Water Suppression methods were used for diagnostic procedures.**Results:** Out of the 60 cases of ring enhancing lesions, 30 were infective lesions while 30 were neoplastic. Out of 60 patients in this study 38 were male and 22 were female. We observed that the cut off of 2.03 mean ADC values provide sensitivity and specificity of 90% and 100% respectively, in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean ADC value of infective RELs was 1.21 +/- 0.47 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 2.35 +/- 0.30. With a cut off of 2.23 mean rCBV values provide sensitivity and specificity of 70% and 80 % respectively, in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean rCBV value of infective RELs was 1.83 +/- 0.77 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 2.85 +/- 1.06. With a cut off value of 1.47 Cho:Cr ratios provide sensitivity and specificity of 86.7% and 90 % respectively, in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean Cho:Cr value of infective RELs was 2.85 +/- 1.06 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 1.23 +/- 0.29.**Conclusions:** Conventional MRI examination provides information on lesion location, homogeneity, signal intensity, presence of perilesional edema, and degree of contrast enhancement. However, it is limited in its ability to depict changes in cell density, cell type, or biochemical composition, perfusion and microstructural heterogeneity which can be investigated using advanced techniques which provide valuable information that complements routine MRI sequences. Hence, advanced MRI Parameters namely DWI, PWI and MRS can be useful tools in differentiating infectious from neoplastic ring enhancing lesions by evaluating the microstructural heterogeneity and other information received in a more comprehensive way. it accurately distinguishes between different types of infective and neoplastic ring-enhancing lesions and it significantly impacts the subsequent management and treatment of the patient.**Keywords:** MRI Techniques, Infective Intracranial Ring Enhancing Lesions, Neoplastic Intracranial Ring Enhancing Lesions.

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Introduction

Ring-enhancing lesions (RELs) are among the most frequently encountered abnormalities on neuroimaging studies worldwide as well as in India, and can occur due to a diverse array of causes including infectious, neoplastic, inflammatory, and vascular diseases [1,2]. On imaging, these lesions are visible as isodense or hypodense mass lesions on non-contrast CT scans. Following contrast administration, there is enhancement in the form of a ring surrounding the hypodense area. Typically, they are situated at the interface of grey and white matter, although they can also be found in subcortical regions, deep white matter, or even superficially on the brain's surface [3].

Conventional MRI examination enables visualization of a mass lesion, providing information on its location, homogeneity, signal intensity, presence of perilesional edema, and degree of contrast enhancement. The inherent high contrast resolution of MRI results in precise delineation of anatomical structures and its capability of generating images in various planes enhances its versatility and diagnostic value. However, conventional MRI is limited in its ability to depict changes in cell density, cell type, or biochemical composition, which can be investigated using advanced techniques which provide valuable information that complements routine MRI scans. Furthermore, conventional MR methods do not have a high sensitivity and specificity making it difficult to precisely diagnose intracranial RELs by these means alone [4].

The role of the most commonly used advanced MR imaging techniques— Diffusion-Weighted Imaging (DWI), perfusion weighted imaging (PWI), and MR Spectroscopy (MRS)— in the diagnosis and classification of the common brain lesions is being explored and the advancements in MRI technology have made a profound impact on the entire practice of neuroscience, greatly enhancing the ability to diagnose, monitor, and guide treatment of various intra-axial brain pathologies [4].

Although initially DWI MRI was introduced for the early detection of stroke, it now has various other clinical applications [5]. When used in conjunction with apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) mapping, DWI provides information about the functional environment of water in tissues, thereby augmenting the morphologic information provided by conventional MR imaging.

For the many mimickers of brain tumors for example granulomas, abscesses, demyelinating lesions and metastasis particularly when solitary, even contrast MR imaging can be misleading as it shows enhancement in any lesion associated with

disruption of the blood-brain barrier (BBB). It is not the true representative of neovascularity or perfusion and does not show true pathological changes [6]. PWI can give detailed structural information and information on tumour perfusion at a cellular level.

MRS also serves as a non-invasive method to characterize tissue by utilizing signals from hydrogen protons to create anatomical images. MRS leverages this data to determine the concentration of brain metabolites like N-acetyl aspartate (NAA), choline (Cho), creatine (Cr), and lactate within the examined tissue. The widespread adoption of faster MRS applications with higher signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) and spatial resolution enables the detection of functional metabolic changes, thereby providing a more detailed understanding of the tumor's nature as well as the morphological and physiological changes occurring in the surrounding brain parenchyma [7].

Additionally, lesions with different underlying pathophysiology may present with similar MRI appearances. Therefore, MRI and DWI, PWI, MRS are complementary tools that can aid in disease diagnosis, monitoring disease progression, and evaluating response to therapy [8]. Objectives of our study was to determine the combined diagnostic performance of advanced MRI Parameters- MRI Diffusion, MRI Perfusion, MR Spectroscopy- in conjunction with conventional MRI sequences for better evaluation of intracranial ring enhancing lesions and differentiation of their infective versus neoplastic etiologies And also deduce the sensitivity and specificity of the combined usage of conventional and advanced MRI techniques in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial ring- enhancing lesions.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Radio Diagnosis, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar during a period from July 2022 to June 2024.

Materials and Methods

Source of Data: Patients referred to the Department of Radio diagnosis with suspected intracranial ring enhancing lesions detected on conventional MRI/ CECT of brain were evaluated through conventional and multi- parametric advanced MRI sequences.

Study Equipment: GE Signa HDxT 1.5 Tesla MRI. 16 Channel NV array head coil was used for the study.

Sample Size: 60 patients

Type of Study: Prospective observational study

Duration of Study: 2 Years.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with intracranial lesions showing ring enhancement on post-contrast MRI brain and who underwent DWI, MRP and MRS.
- Patients with incidentally diagnosed ring enhancing lesions on CECT brain which showed ring enhancement on post-contrast MRI study and underwent DWI, MRP and MRS.
- Patients who underwent surgical resection/ aspiration/ biochemical analysis.
- Patients willing for short- term follow ups to assess treatment response.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients in whom MRI was contraindicated (history of metallic implants/ cardiac pacemaker insertion and metallic foreign body in situ).
- Patients presenting with trauma (head injury), and those with clinical signs suggestive of hemorrhagic or ischemic infarcts of brain.
- Uncooperative patients who could not undergo MRI for the duration of the required additional sequences and in whom good quality imaging was not possible.
- Patients with deranged renal function.

Methodology:

Patient Preparation

- A satisfactory written informed consent was obtained from the patient, following which detailed history was taken.
- Patient's renal function test, old investigations and prior treatment received were referred to.
- Before entering the scanner room the patient was asked to remove all metal object including keys, coins, wallet, any cards with magnetic strips, jewellery, hearing aid and hairpins, and then changed into a hospital gown.
- An intravenous line was placed with extension tubing extending out of the magnetic bore when contrast MRI is planned.

Positioning

- Patient was positioned in supine position with head pointing towards the magnet.

Imaging protocol:

Conventional MR Sequences: Conventional T1, T2, FLAIR images were obtained with TR/ TE being 2500/ 44, 5000/ 99, 9000/99 respectively. Matrix size of 128x128, slice thickness 5.0 mm, 1.5

mm gap, flip angle 140, voxel size 0.7 mm x 0.7 mm x 5.0 mm was used. Post-contrast images were obtained using multi-planar T1 FS (TR/TE 1970/44; Slice thickness 5 mm with 2 mm gap) and 3D BRAVO (TR/TE 1890/5.6; Slice thickness 1 mm with 0.5 mm gap) sequences.

Advanced MR Sequences:

Diffusion weighted imaging: DWI was done using 2D echoplanar imaging. Images were obtained at two b values 0 & 1000 in x, y, z direction. TR/TE was 4100/89. Slice thickness was 4.5 mm with gap of 1.6 mm. FOV was 230 mm. Voxel size was 1.2 mm x 1.2 mm x 4.5 mm. SNR of 1 was obtained. Minimum ADC value was determined from the central portion of the lesion.

Dynamic MR Perfusion Imaging: DSC MRI was performed using a T2*-weighted single-shot gradient-echo echo-planar imaging during contrast medium Gadobutrol (Gadovist) administration. Parameters of the sequence were TR/TE of 1500/30 ms, FOV of 240 x 240 mm, matrix size of 96 x 128, slice thickness of 5 mm, interslice gap of 0, flip angle of 60, number of slices of 26, acquisition time of 80 s, and 53 images

were obtained at intervals equal to the repetition time. After 7 s, a 18-ml contrast bolus was administered intravenously using an MR compatible power injector at a rate of 5 ml/s, and immediately followed by a 15-ml bolus of saline injected at a rate of 5 ml/s through an antecubital angio catheter.

The measurements of CBV were obtained from perfusion maps using ROIs. The ROIs positioned on the CBV maps were then automatically transferred onto the corresponding post-contrast T1-weighted image dataset in order to ensure that we have placed the ROIs correctly in enhancing wall of the lesion. Multiple measurements were manually drawn in areas with maximum signal enhancement on color-coded DSC CBV maps, and the highest CBV values were obtained from these ROIs. To minimize confounding factors in CBV analysis, the size of the ROIs were kept constant (12x12 pixels, 17.58 mm²). The ROIs were selected from within the tumor and the contralateral normal appearing white matter avoiding as far as possible areas of necrotic tissue, cysts, or large vessels. The rCBV ratios were calculated by dividing the maximum value in the tumor by the value in the contralateral normal-appearing white matter.

Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy: Multi-voxel MRS was done using intermediate TE 2D chemical shift imaging with TR 1690, TE 135 ms, flip angle 90, band width 1000 Hz, vector size 1024, voxel size 11.4 mm x11.4 mm x15 mm. Total scanning time was 6 minute, 5 second. Spectroscopy

imaging was done post contrast and good quality spectra from contrast enhancing- wall of lesions were included in this study. Care was taken not to include CSF or surrounding bones. We used T1 post contrast sequence as localization sequence with 5 mm thickness.

Water Suppression: As water is most abundant and thus its signal in MRS spectrum is much higher than that of other metabolites (the signal of water is 100.000 times greater than that of other metabolites). To avoid this high peak from water to be superimposed on the signal of other brain metabolites, water suppression techniques were used. The technique what we used was Chemical shift selective water suppression (CHESS) which pre-saturates water signal using frequency selective 90° pulses before the localizing pulse sequence.

PRESS – Point Resolved Spectroscopy technique was used.

Voxel Selection: Both Single and Multivoxel techniques were used. For small focal lesions (like Tuberculoma) Single voxel was selected and for large lesions (like GBM) multivoxels were used. For neoplastic lesions the voxel was placed in the most enhancing portion of the lesion and for inflammatory lesions like abscess, voxel was placed in the core of the lesion.

Once the complete analysis of plain and contrast MR was done, spectroscopy of the lesion was analyzed. Visualization of the elevated peaks of the metabolites in addition to analysis of the numerical

values of the metabolite ratios mainly Ch/Cr was done.

The morphologic and multiparametric data was later tabulated in the master chart and individual imaging feature was analyzed and results were analyzed for the final radiological diagnosis. The findings were correlated with histopathology or biochemical parameters to calculate their diagnostic performance.

Patients on ATT were followed up with MRI examinations between 3 to 6 months to assess initial response. Patients with primary brain tumors underwent surgery or stereotactic biopsy. Those with metastases were evaluated to locate the primary site, and those without a primary site were subjected to stereotactic biopsy with histopathology confirming metastasis.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed by using SPSS version 23 software. Qualitative data was represented in the form of frequency and percentage. Quantitative data was represented using Mean ± SD. Optimal cut-off and screening efficacy of the ADC were computed via ROC curve analysis taking histopathology as gold standard. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as level of significance.

Observations

A total of 60 patients presented with ring enhancing lesions, out of which 30 were infective lesions while 30 were neoplastic. Out of 60 patients in this study 38 were male and 22 were female.

Table 1. Size distribution of various ring enhancing lesions

Size	Infective		Neoplastic		P Value
<2cm	20	66.7%	7	23.3%	0.001
2-4 cm	8	26.7%	10	33.3%	
>4cm	2	6.7%	13	43.3%	

In case of multiple ring enhancing lesions, size of the maximum number of lesions falling in a category was considered

Figure 1: Laterality of lesions

A majority, ie 38 (63%) of the cases had T1 hypointense lesions. Isointense lesions were seen in 10 (16%) cases, followed by hyperintensity in 8 (13%) cases and mixed signal intensity in 4 (6%) cases.

Figure 2: T1 Signal Intensity of various RELs

Table 2. Distribution of lesions according to t2 morphology

T2WI	Total Cases	Mixed Intensity		Hypointense		Hyperintense		Isointense	
Abscess	10	2	20.0%	1	10.0%	7	70.0%	0	0.0%
Glioma	14	4	28.5%	0	0.0%	10	71.4%	0	0.0%
Metastases	13	1	7.7%	1	7.7%	11	84.6%	0	0.0%
NCC	3	0	0.0%	1	33.3%	2	66.7%	0	0.0%
Tuberculoma	18	0	0.0%	7	38.9%	10	55.6%	1	5.6%
Tumor Recurrence	2	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	100.0%	0	0.0%

T2 hyperintense lesions were seen in majority of the patients, ie 42 (70%), whilst hypointense lesions were seen in 10 (16%) cases, followed by mixed signal intensity in 7 cases (11%) and isointensity in 1 case.

Figure 3: Grading of Perilesional Edema in RELs

Table 3: Distribution of lesions according to midline shift

Midline Shift	Absent	Present	P Value
Infective	73.3%	26.7%	0.018
Neoplastic	43.3%	56.7%	

Figure 4: Midline shift in RELs

Table 4. Distribution of lesions according to post- contrast wall enhancement characteristics

	Abscess	Glioma	Metastases	NCC	Tuberculoma	Tumor Recurrence	P Value
Thin-Irregular	n	0	2	0	0	0	<0.001
	%	0.0%	0.0%	15.4%	0.0%	0.0%	
Thin-Smooth	n	6	4	3	11	0	
	%	60.0%	30.8%	100%	61.1%	0.0%	
Thin-Smooth, Conglomerated	n	2	0	0	7	0	
	%	20.0%	0.0%	0.0%	38.9%	0.0%	
Thick-Irregular	n	2	2	0	0	0	
	%	20.0%	15.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
Thick-Irregular, Nodular	n	0	5	0	0	2	
	%	0.0%	38.5%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
Thick-Smooth, Conglomerated	n	0	0	0	0	0	
	%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	

Figure 5: Post- Contrast Wall Characteristics of RELs

Table 5: Distribution of cases according to morphology of diffusion restriction on dwi/adc sequences

Diffusion Restriction	Total Cases	Absent		Present		P Value
Infective	30	13	43.3%	17	56.70%	<0.001
Neoplastic	30	6	20.0%	24	80%	

Table 6: Metabolite peaks observed on mrs various rels

Metabolite	Infective	Neoplastic	P Value
Choline	10.0%	83.3%	<0.001
Reduced NAA	56.7%	96.7%	<0.001
Lipid- Lactate	86.7%	80.0%	0.488
Amino Acids	33.30%	3.30%	0.013

Figure 6: Metabolite peaks observed in RELs on MRS

Table 7: Mean overall value of advanced mri parameters

	ADC	rCBV	Cho:Cr
Mean	1.78	2.34	1.75
Standard Deviation	0.69	1.05	0.84

Figure 7: Mean values of Advanced Techniques in various RELs compared with HPE/ Biochemical Results

Table 8: Mean value of advanced mri parameters among lesion categories

Lesion Category Based On Maging		Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
ADC	Infective	1.21	0.47	<0.001
	Neoplastic	2.35	0.30	
rCBV	Infective	1.83	0.77	<0.001
	Neoplastic	2.85	1.06	
Cho:Cr	Infective	1.23	0.29	<0.001
	Neoplastic	2.28	0.88	

Statistical analysis demonstrated that with a cut off of 2.03 mean ADC values provide sensitivity and specificity of 90% and 100% respectively, in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean ADC value of infective RELs was 1.21 +/- 0.47 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 2.35 +/- 0.30.

With a cut off of 2.23 mean rCBV values provide sensitivity and specificity of 70% and 80 % respectively, in differentiating infective from

neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean rCBV value of infective RELs was 1.83 +/- 0.77 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 2.85 +/- 1.06

With a cut off value of 1.47 Cho:Cr ratios provide sensitivity and specificity of 86.7% and 90 % respectively, in differentiating infective from neoplastic intracranial RELs. The mean Cho:Cr value of infective RELs was 2.85 +/- 1.06 while that of Neoplastic RELs was 1.23 +/- 0.29.

Table 9: Auc, confidence interval, sensitivity, specificity, and cutoffs of advanced mri parameters

Advanced Parameter	AUC	P Value	95% Confidence Interval		Sensitivity	Specificity	Cut off
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
ADC	0.978	<0.001	0.948	1.000	90	100	2.02
rCBV	0.767	<0.001	0.647	0.886	70	80	2.23
Cho:Cr	0.903	<0.001	0.818	0.989	86.7	90	1.47

Figure 8. ROC curve of Advanced MRI Parameters

Table 10: Mean, standard deviation and confidence interval of advanced mri parameters in intracranial ring- enhancing lesions

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum	P Value
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
ADC	Abscess	10	0.59	0.17	0.47	0.71	0.42	0.83	<0.001
	Glioma	14	2.55	0.10	2.49	2.60	2.42	2.78	
	Metastases	13	2.31	0.05	2.28	2.34	2.25	2.43	
	NCC	3	1.40	0.01	1.38	1.42	1.39	1.41	
	Tuberculoma	18	1.54	0.13	1.48	1.61	1.37	1.80	
	Tumor Recurrence	2	1.62	0.02	1.48	1.76	1.61	1.63	
	Total	60	1.78	0.69	1.60	1.96	0.42	2.78	
rCBV	Abscess	10	1.61	1.25	0.72	2.51	0.02	3.45	<0.001
	Glioma	14	3.32	1.29	2.58	4.06	1.60	5.63	
	Metastases	13	2.35	0.59	1.99	2.71	1.63	3.94	
	NCC	3	1.52	0.53	0.20	2.84	1.02	2.08	
	Tuberculoma	18	2.04	0.30	1.89	2.19	1.65	2.63	
	Tumor Recurrence	2	2.90	0.68	-3.19	8.99	2.42	3.38	
	Total	60	2.34	1.05	2.07	2.61	0.02	5.63	
Cho:Cr	Abscess	10	1.15	0.12	1.06	1.24	0.96	1.28	<0.001
	Glioma	14	2.58	0.97	2.02	3.14	1.20	4.09	
	Metastases	13	2.10	0.71	1.67	2.53	1.45	3.23	
	NCC	3	0.91	0.04	0.82	1.00	0.87	0.94	
	Tuberculoma	18	1.30	0.34	1.13	1.47	0.82	1.97	
	Tumor Recurrence	2	2.08	0.45	-1.93	6.08	1.76	2.39	
	Total	60	1.75	0.84	1.54	1.97	0.82	4.09	

Table 11: Diagnostic utility test results of advanced mri in infective vs neoplastic ring-enhancing lesions

		Lesion Category On Hpe/ Biochemical Analysis		Total	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	P Value
		Infective	Neoplastic						
		n							
Lesion Category On MR	Infective	n	29	1	96.67	96.67	96.67	96.67	<0.001
		%	96.7%	3.3%					
	Neoplastic	n	1	29					
		%	3.3%	96.7%					

The overall sensitivity and specificity of advanced MRI techniques in conjunction with conventional sequences in differentiating infective versus neoplastic intracranial ring enhancing lesions was 96.7 %, with a p value of <0.001.

Figure 9: Pyogenic abscess with epidural empyema and pachymeningitis.

DSC- MRP: Shows no significant increased rCBV in the enhancing rim of the abscess, along with an area of relative hypoperfusion in the perilesional edema.

MV MR spectroscopy at intermediate TE shows relatively depleted NAA, choline, and creatine

within the necrotic core and elevated peaks corresponding to lipids/lactate (0.9-1.3).

SV MRS shows the peaks of succinate (3.4), acetate (1.9), and cytosolic amino acids (alanine-1.3; valine, leucine, and isoleucine-0.9)

Figure 10: A well-defined lesion is noted in right frontal lobe which appears hypointense on T1 and hyperintense on T2 weighted imaging. Its wall shows smooth, complete T2 & SWI hypointensity. On FLAIR hyperintense signal is seen in the cavity along with marked perilesional oedema causing mass effect and midline shift towards left. Post-contrast images show thin, uniform peripheral ring enhancement corresponding to the T2 hypointense capsule having smooth inner and outer margins. Few pockets of epidural abscess/ empyema are also seen along the right frontal convexity with associated pachymeningeal thickening and enhancement. DWI/ ADC sequences showed central homogenous true diffusion restriction within the abscess cavity (ADC value of $0.3769 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}^2$).

Discussions

The present study was differentiated the infective versus neoplastic causes of intracranial ring enhancing lesions, 60 patients were evaluated and made to undergo conventional and advanced MR Imaging techniques. The final radiological diagnosis was correlated with histopathological results for neoplastic causes and biochemical findings for infective causes (reference standard).

Patients' age group ranged from 7 to 77 years. The highest incidence of RELs was found in age group >60yrs accounting for of 26% cases and the least incidence was seen in age group of 0-10 years constituting 4% of patients.

Males accounted for 63% (n=37) of the total cases while females accounted for 37% (n=23). 70% of the infective RELs were encountered in males, as compared to 30% in females, whilst 57% of neoplastic RELs were encountered in males as compared to 43% in females. This was in agreement with a previous study on RELs by Rudresh et al [9] which found a male preponderance. In another study by Chaoshuang L et al [10]. men were more affected than women.

Vomiting was the most common presenting complaint in 41% of cases followed by headache (40%), seizures and weakness (37%), altered sensorium (29%), fever (27%), focal deficits (12%), ataxia (10%) and visual disturbance (3%).

Out of the 60 patients with RELs evaluated, Tuberculoma (n= 18) was the commonest REL (30%), followed by Glioma (n=14, 23%), Metastasis (n= 13, 21%), Abscess (n= 10, 16%), NCC (n= 3, 5%) and Tumour Recurrence (n= 2, 3%). In a study conducted by Schwartz et al [11] 40% cases were gliomas. The higher incidence of tuberculomas is possibly due to the higher prevalence of tuberculosis in India. A possible explanation for less number of metastatic lesions lies in the fact that most common primaries like lung and breast cancers are not routinely subjected to MRI brain until the patient presents with CNS symptoms. Among the sixty patients with RELs noted 40 (67%) were unilateral, 19 (32%) were bilateral while 1 case of tuberculoma (1%) was located in the midline cerebellum alone. 30 patients (50%) presented with a single lesion, 2-4 lesions were noted in 14 (23%) cases and > 4 RELs were seen in 16 (27%) cases.

Among the sixty patients evaluated - majority 27 (45%) of them showed RELs <2cm, 18 (30%) of them showed lesions of sizes between 2-4 cm and only in 15 (25%) lesions size is greater than 4 cm. In case of multiple lesions size of the maximum number of lesions which were falling in one category were considered. A difference in size distribution between infective and neoplastic

causes of ring-enhancing lesions was noted. Infective lesions appeared to be more commonly smaller than 2cm, with 20 out of 30 (67%) falling into this category. In contrast, neoplastic lesions were much more frequently larger than 4cm, with 13 out of 30 (44%) falling into this category, compared to only 7.7% for infective lesions.

Infective lesions tended to have mild- to- moderate perilesional edema, ie 23 out of 30 cases (76.9%) while only 4 cases (13%) were categorized as having severe and 3 (10%) as having disproportionate edema. On a similar note, neoplastic lesions exhibited mild to moderate edema in 19 out of 30 cases (63%), while 7 (10%) had disproportionate and 4 cases (13%) had severe edema. Midline shift was seen in 42% of total REL cases, while it was absent in the majority (58%) of cases. Among the 42% cases in which it was observed, 57% were neoplastic and 27% were infective. Amongst neoplastic causes, midline shift was caused by gliomas in 85% cases, metastases in 30%, and in recurrent tumors 50% cases. Amongst the infective causes, 11% of tuberculomas and 6% of abscesses were shown to cause midline shift.

72% of overall cases had well- defined walls, whilst 28% were ill- defined. All the NCC (n=3) and pyogenic abscess (n – 5) showed thin-smooth and lobulated walls. Among the tubercular abscess as well (n – 4) the outer margin was smooth. In fungal abscess (n – 1) the outer margin of the thick wall was irregular. Intracavitary projection was seen arising from the wall which was T1-isointense and T2- hypointense. No projections were seen in the pyogenic or tubercular abscess. Luthra et al [7] studied the comparative evaluation of fungal, tubercular and pyogenic brain abscess and they found intracavitary projections from the wall of fungal abscess which was isointense to hypointense on T1 weighted and hypointense on T2 weighted images. We found similar observation in our study. 61% of tuberculomas showed thin-smooth walls. On postcontrast T1-weighted images, there were single or multiple conglomerate ring enhancements within 39% of tuberculoma patients. 92% of gliomas and 100% of tumor recurrence had thick- irregular and nodular walls. Metastases had varying wall morphology with a thin-irregular wall observed in 15% cases, thin-smooth wall in 30% cases, thick-irregular wall in 15% cases and thick-irregular wall with nodularity in 38% cases. Our findings were similar to the study conducted by Vieth RG et al [12].

Diffusion Weighted Imaging

Out of the sixty patients evaluated– 41 (68%) of patients had diffusion restricting lesions (central in 17 and peripheral in 24 patients), while 19 (32%) cases showed no diffusion restriction. Central pattern of diffusion restriction was noted in 43% of

infective and 13 % of neoplastic conditions, while peripheral pattern of restriction was observed in 67% neoplastic and 13% infective conditions. The mean ADC value of normal-appearing white matter in our study was $0.76 \pm 0.08 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. The mean ADC value of CSF was $3.2 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.3 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. Mean ADC value of CSF was $3.2 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.3 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$.

The mean ADC value of total infective lesions in our study was $1.21 \pm 0.47 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, while the mean ADC value of overall neoplastic lesions in this study was $2.35 \pm 0.30 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ which gave a sensitivity of 90% and a Specificity of 100%. ADC cut off of $2.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ was arrived at with values below the cutoff being common for infective RELs and values above the cutoff being common for neoplastic RELs. The mean ADC value of brain abscess was $0.59 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. In pyogenic abscess the mean ADC value was $0.461 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and in tubercular abscess the mean ADC value was $0.785 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. In fungal abscess the mean ADC value was $0.727 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. NCC had a mean ADC value of $1.40 \pm 1.622 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. In case of tuberculoma the mean ADC value was $1.54 \pm 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$.

In our study, the abscess cavity showed hyperintensities on DWI and hypointensities on ADC maps. These findings were comparable to the studies done by Ebisu et al [13], Lai et al [14], and Cartes-Zumelzu et al [15].

In our study, majority of granulomas showed hyperintensities without restricted diffusion on DWI except 4 cases of tuberculoma (caseating liquefied) which showed central restriction. The mean ADC value of tuberculoma in our study was $1.54 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. R K Gupta et al [16] categorized tuberculoma into three groups depending on the intensity in the core of the lesion on T2 weighted images. They found that the mean ADC from core of T2 hypointense lesions was $1.24 \pm 0.32 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, mean ADC value from mildly T2 hyperintense was $0.80 \pm 0.08 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and mean ADC value from T2 hyperintense was $0.74 \pm 0.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$.

The mean ADC value of NCC $1.40 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. Reduced diffusion possibly is a hallmark of a viscous or proteinaceous content, which is expected during degeneration of a cystic NCC lesion. Our study correlated with previous study by R K Gupta et al [16] in which they found that the ADC values from the core of vesicular and degenerating stages of NCC showed $1.66 \pm 0.29 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $1.51 \pm 0.23 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, respectively.

In neoplastic group glioma mean ADC value was $2.55 \pm 2.521 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. In case of metastasis, 9 (69%) cases showed peripheral diffusion restriction. Mean ADC value was $2.31 \pm 2.308 \times 10^{-3}$

mm^2/s . In Tumour recurrence, mean ADC value was $1.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$.

In our study atypical findings were detected in 33% of cases of high grade gliomas with mean ADC value of 2.55. 2 cases glioblastoma studied by J.S Reddy et al [17] showed hyperintensity in DWI with an ADC value of $0.92 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ which was inconsistent with the diagnosis of neoplastic lesions. 1 case of glioma in our study showed similar central pattern of restricted diffusion with an ADC value of 1.53 which on HPE turned out to be fungal abscess.

Recurrent tumors were found to have a mean ADC value of $1.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, which was comparable to a study done by Xu et al [18] in which the presence of a recurrent tumor was suggested by either an ADC ratio less than 1.65 or a fractional anisotropy ratio greater than 0.36 in the contrast-enhanced lesion.

MR Perfusion

The mean rCBV value our study was 2.34 ± 1.05 which gave a sensitivity of 70%, specificity of 80% and rCBV cut off of 2.23 with values below the cutoff being common infective RELs and values above the cutoff being common for neoplastic RELs. The mean rCBV value of total infective lesions in our study was 1.83 ± 0.77 .

The mean rCBV value from the peripheral wall of tuberculoma was 2.04 ± 0.30 . This was in accordance with the study conducted by Sankhe S et al [19]. The raised rCBV values were consistent with the histopathological progression of the tubercular lesions and correlated with increased angiogenic activity in its cellular portion secondary to increased expression of vascular endothelial growth factor (Gupta RK et al [16]). The low rCBV value in the perilesional edema is due to vasoconstriction secondary to the raised interstitial pressure.

The mean rCBV value of abscess was 1.61 ± 1.25 which was similar to a study conducted by Toh CH et al [20] who found a cutoff of 1.45 ± 1.17 .

The mean rCBV value of metastases was 2.35 ± 0.59 which was similar to a study conducted by Toh CH et al [20], who found a value of 2.39 ± 0.90 in their study.

The mean rCBV value of tumor recurrence was 2.90 ± 0.68 . This was in concordance with a study by Metaweh et al [21], DSC MR perfusion was able to differentiate newly developed/enlarging enhancing mass lesion in patients with previous history of brain tumor and surgery followed by radio therapy (+/- chemotherapy) as recurrent tumor or radiation necrosis using the cut off value of rCBV of 1.8 with sensitivity 77.8%, specificity

80%, positive predictive value PPV 93.3%, negative predictive value 50% and efficacy 78.3%.

MR Spectroscopy

The mean Cho:Cr in our study was 1.75 \pm 0.84 which gave a sensitivity of 87%, specificity of 90% and Cho:Cr cut off of 1.47 with values below the cutoff being common for infective RELs and values above the cutoff being common for neoplastic RELs.

Out of the sixty patients evaluated, choline peak was observed in 28 cases, reduced NAA peak in 46 cases, Lipid-Lactate peak in 50 cases and amino acids in 11 cases.

The mean Cho:Cr value of total infective lesions in our study was 1.23 \pm 0.29.

In our study the mean Cho: Cr ratio of abscess was 1.15 \pm 0.12. They showed absence of Cho, Cr, with reduced NAA and increased concentrations of various amino acids (acetate, alanine, lactate, isoleucine, leucine, trehalose) in 70% cases. Lipid-lactate peak was observed in 70% of all abscess. This was similar to study by Ghosh et al [22] found that the Cho/Cr ratio was lower in abscesses compared to gliomas, with a mean Cho/Cr ratio of 0.6-1.2 in abscesses.

The mean Cho: Cr ratio of tuberculoma was 1.30 \pm 0.34. This was similar to study by Parry et al [23] who found a ratio of 1.36 \pm 0.41.

MRS showed a Lipid peak in all cases of tuberculomas and it plays an important role in identification of tuberculomas from other infective granulomas. The stage of the tuberculoma (whether caseous or non caseous) could be identified with the help of T2 weighted images. Jayasundar R et al [24] concluded that presence of lipid can be used for differentiating tuberculomas from both nonspecific inflammatory granuloma and NCC. Additionally, NAA was reduced in 50% cases.

The mean Cho: Cr ratio of NCC was 0.91 \pm 0.04 which was similar to study by Parry et al [23] who got 0.95. 2 out of the 3 cases of intraparenchymal NCC showed reduced NAA peak, while 1 case showed normal metabolite spectra. Cho / Cr ratio was less than 1.1 in all NCC and more than 1.2 in all cases tuberculoma which is similar to the study performed by Kumar et al [25] and Jayasunder et al [24].

The mean Cho:Cr value of overall neoplastic lesions in this study was 2.28 \pm 0.88. The mean Cho: Cr ratio of glioma was 2.58 \pm 0.97. This was similar to study by Dashottar et al [26] on MRS, who found mean Cho/Cr ratios of 2.87 \pm 0.98. Choline peak was observed in all 14 cases with a lipid-lactate peak in 11 (78%) cases and reduced NAA in 13 (92%) cases. There was high choline/Cr

ratio and high choline in the surrounding oedema as well, similar to a study done by Lai et al [14].

The mean Cho: Cr ratio of metastases was 2.10 \pm 0.71. This was similar to the study by Parry et al who reported 2.63 \pm 0.99 and Morales et al [26] 2.1 \pm 0.6. Amongst metastases, all the cases showed elevated Choline, with reduced NAA in 92% cases and lipid-lactate peak in 62 % cases.

The mean Cho: Cr ratio of tumor recurrence was 2.08 \pm 0.45, while the mean Cho: NAA ratio was 3.9. In a study conducted by Plotkin M et al [27] a combined diagnostic threshold of a choline-creatine ratio greater than 1.11 and a choline-N-acetyl aspartate ratio greater than 1.17 resulted in 89% sensitivity and 83% specificity for identifying tumor, with Cho: Cr and Cho: NAA ratios being significantly higher in recurrent tumor than in radiation necrosis [28].

Conclusion

Conventional MRI examination provides information on lesion location, homogeneity, signal intensity, presence of perilesional edema, and degree of contrast enhancement. However, it is limited in its ability to depict changes in cell density, cell type, or biochemical composition, perfusion and microstructural heterogeneity which can be investigated using advanced techniques which provide valuable information that complements routine MRI sequences. Hence, advanced MRI Parameters namely DWI, PWI and MRS can be useful tools in differentiating infectious from neoplastic ring enhancing lesions by evaluating the microstructural heterogeneity and other information received in a more comprehensive way. It accurately distinguishes between different types of infective and neoplastic ring-enhancing lesions and it significantly impacts the subsequent management and treatment of the patient.

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